

SUPER-CRITICAL AND ULTRA SUPER-CRITICAL THERMAL STEAM POWER PLANTS - ADVANTAGES AND CHALLENGES

Soupayan Mitra¹, Sudipta Dutta²

Jalpaiguri Government Engineering College (JGEC), MAKAUT, Jalpaiguri-735102, W.B., India^{1,2}

Professor of Mechanical Engineering Department, JGEC¹

Student, 6th Semester (3rd Year), Mechanical Engineering Department, JGEC²

E-mail: soupayan.mitra@me.jgec.ac.in¹ sd2616@me.jgec.ac.in²

ABSTRACT

Super-critical (SC) and Ultra Super-critical (USC) are modern steam generators (SG) that operate at pressure above the critical point of water (22.06 MPa pressure, 374°C temperature). At this pressure, water directly turns into steam without forming bubbles. The technologies of these thermal steam generators are continuously developing and under extensive research. SC and USC steam generators have advantages of generation of large power from a single plant with higher efficiency, lower pollution emission and lower operating cost per unit power generation compared to sub-critical (SBC) steam generators. However, initial cost of SC and USC steam generators are higher than that of SBC. Also SC and USC steam generators still have some technological and operational challenges. In the present investigation, basic thermodynamic operation principle of SC, USC and SBC steam generators are at first briefly stated. A comparison between SC/USC and SBC steam generators are discussed considering various aspects. Challenges before SC and USC steam generators are elaborated and their possible solutions are outlined.

KEYWORDS: Sub-critical, Super-critical, Ultra super-critical Steam power plant, Comparison, Challenges

1 INTRODUCTION

Energy is the propelling force of civilization. Electricity is the most useful form of energy. Still date most of the electricity is produced by burning coal in thermal steam power generators in India and most of the other major countries and expectedly the status of coal will remain almost same for some coming decades. Super-critical (SC) and Ultra super-critical (USC) thermal steam power plants are advanced types of steam generators, operate well above critical point of water (22.06 bar pressure, 374°C temperature). In fact, its operating pressures and temperatures normally ranges from 24 to 30 MPa and from 570°C to 600°C respectively and above i.e., highly superheated. For Sub-critical (SBC) boilers or, steam generators, operating pressure is much below of critical pressure of water i.e., below 22.06 bar; however, operating temperatures are in superheated condition. For large capacity steam plants, normally from 500 MW and above, SC and USC boilers are preferred mainly due to its higher thermal efficiency, reduced pollution effects and for lower per unit generation operating cost. However, some important challenges are still there before SC and USC plants for its smooth and cost effective operations and to augment its capacity further to get still higher efficiency associated with lower emission. A lot of research is going on this subject and new effective findings are coming out. Some papers in this regard may be referred here like by Bhiogade D. S. (2023), by Cenușă and Opris (2025), by Mohamed O. et al. (2020), by Opris I. et al. (2020), by Piwowarski M.(2009), by Wang C. et al. (2025) and others.

2 SUB-CRITICAL AND SUPER-CRITICAL BOILERS

Both sub-critical and super-critical boilers as well as higher capacity ultra super-critical steam power plants operate on Rankine cycle. The basic T-S (Temperature-Entropy) diagrams are shown in Figure 1.

In Figure 1, the left side diagram is for sub-critical and right side diagram is for super-critical (SC) as well as for ultra super-critical (USC) steam plant. The basic difference between the two is that in Sub-critical (SBC) case, operating pressure remains below water critical point 'C' (22.06 MPa) and for super-critical plant pressure is well above critical pressure. For both the cases, final steam temperature is highly superheated corresponding to their respecting operating pressures. In super-critical boiler, water does not boil or condense inside the boiler zone, here whole water is directly converted into steam and then superheated, remaining in a super-critical state, and then drives the turbines. Hence, no boiler drum is required for SC and USC plants to separate saturated water and steam. The cycle is more efficient than SBC plant due to the absence of phase changes (latent heat is zero) in the boiler and for higher pressure and higher mean temperature of heat addition. For SBC plant water boils at a comparatively lower pressure and temperature in boiler water walls, and then saturated steam portion is separated in the boiler drum. From drum saturated liquid water again goes down through down-comers and then rises again through water walls creating a portion of saturated steam, which again separated in drum. From drum saturated steam goes to superheaters and become superheated, which then drives the turbine. The SBC plant cycle efficiency is lower due to the phase change from liquid to steam and for comparatively lower pressure & lower mean heat addition temperature.

Figure 1. T-S diagrams for sub-critical and super-critical/ultra super-critical steam plants (Web-1)

2.1 Comparison between Sub-critical and Super-critical/ Ultra super-critical steam plants

A comparison between sub-critical and super-critical/ultra super-critical steam power plants are given below in tabular form in Table 1.

Table 1. Comparison between Super-critical/Ultra Super-critical and Sub-critical steam power plants

Feature	Super-critical (SC) and Ultra Super-critical (USC) steam power plant	Sub-critical (SBC) steam power plant
Operating Pressure	Above 22.06 MPa [For SC and USC, typically pressure are around 24 to 26 MPa and 27 to 30 MPa; temperature are around 560 ⁰ C & to some extent more, and 600 ⁰ C & more respectively.	Pressure is below 22.06 MPa (pressure and operating superheated temperature vary depending on capacity of the plant.
Application	Large power plants (typically starts from 500 MW)	Conventional plants (from small to maximum 500 MW or, so)
Latent Heat addition (basically loss)	Nil	Heat addition more

Plant Start up time	Comparatively more	Less		
Boiler Drum	Not Required	Required to separate saturated steam & water		
Overall Plant Efficiency	High. For SC plant typically 40 to 45 % and for USC plant typically 45 to 50%	Low. Typically 31 to 37%. [31% or lower range efficiencies are for small capacity plants]		
Specific coal consumption (coal required per unit power generation)	Low	Comparatively high		
Water consumption per unit power generation	Low	Comparatively high		
Circulation ratio	1 (one)	Assisted Circulation = 3 to 4. Natural Circulation = 7 to 10		
Emission (CO ₂ , SO _x , NO _x and PM) per unit power generation [Data taken from Timm R. (2006, AEP Report), Emission Comparison considering Sub-Bituminous Coal] (1 lb = 0.453592 kg)	Lower for SC & USC Comparatively higher for SBC			
	Emission	Ultra SC	Supercritical	Subcritical
	SO ₂	0.91 lb/MWh	0.97 lb/MWh	0.99 lb/MWh
	NO _x	0.64 lb/MWh	0.68 lb/MWh	0.70 lb/MWh
Boiler and Turbine designs	More advanced designs required	Standard design technologies are mostly available		
Initial investment for a plant	Higher	Lower		
Operational Cost per unit power generation	Lower	Comparatively higher due to lower efficiency		
Control mechanism	Complex advanced and precise control mechanism required	Less complex and normally standardised and matured control mechanism available		
Boiler and Superheater etc. tube materials	Quite costly special alloy steels required due to higher pressure and temperature. USC plants normally use costly spiral tubes for boiler water walls.	Less costly due to comparatively lower pressure and temperature. Normally carbon steel is used for boiler water walls.		

3 SOME EXAMPLES OF SUPER-CRITICAL (SC) AND ULTRA SUPER-CRITICAL (USC) THERMAL STEAM POWER PLANTS

Following are examples of a few Super-critical (SC) and Ultra Super-critical (USC) thermal power plants in India and abroad:

- a) Vindhyachal SC Thermal Power Plant (Madhya Pradesh, India): 800 MW x 6 units, Operating pressure and temperatures are 25 MPa, 570⁰C respectively.
- b) Mundra SC Thermal Power Plant (Gujrat, India): 800 MW x 5 units, Operating pressure and temperatures are 24 to 26 MPa, 570⁰C respectively.
- c) Khargone USC (India's first Ultra Super-critical steam power plant, owned by NTPC), located at Khargone (Selda village locality), Khargone district, Madhya Pradesh, India : 660 MW x 2 units. Operating pressure and temperatures are 27 MPa, 600⁰C respectively.
- d) Xiantao USC Thermal Power Plant (China): 1000 MW x 1 unit. Operating pressure and temperatures are 28 MPa, 600⁰C respectively.
- e) Matsuura USC Thermal Power Plant (Japan): 1000 MW x 1 unit. Operating pressure and temperatures are 28 MPa , 600⁰C respectively.

4 CHALLENGES RELATED TO SUPER-CRITICAL (SC) AND ULTRA SUPER-CRITICAL (USC) THERMAL STEAM POWER PLANTS AND POSSIBLE SOLUTIONS

Super-critical and Ultra Super-critical steam generation units, particularly the boilers, face some challenges because of its extreme operating conditions having very high operating pressure and temperature.

Some key challenges and their possible mitigation or, solutions are given below:

a) **Water Chemistry Control :**

Challenging issues: SC and USC boilers i.e., steam generators need ultra-pure feed water to prevent extremely detrimental scaling, fouling and corrosion due to their very high operating conditions. The water quality requires extremely low levels of dissolved solids like chlorides, sulfates, sodium (all should be below 3 ppb), and silica (below 10 ppb). These can be typically achieved through an oxygenated feed water treatment process, with conductivity ideally below 0.1 mmho. Since these boilers are once-through boilers, unlike sub-critical boilers there is no scope for intermittent and/or continuous blow-down, the feed water must be of ultra-pure desired quality from the very beginning of the water-steam circuit. A slightly alkaline pH is required (around 8.8 to 10) to form a protective oxide layer on the boiler surface.

Possible solution: Required further state-of-the-art research to meticulously maintain stringent water quality for present USC boilers and for further augmentation of operating conditions to get further enhanced efficiency with reduced pollution. Development of possible design may be thought of to incorporate intermitted and/or continuous blow down in the circuit to ease proper maintenance of water quality.

b) **Material selection and corrosion & erosion :**

Challenging issues: The elevated operating conditions due to very high pressure and temperature in SC and USC boilers develop intense stress on materials. Formation of corrosive type compounds like sodium carbonate (Na_2CO_3) and the effects of high-temperature oxidation and erosion can cause detrimental damage to boiler materials.

Possible solution: To use advanced special types of high-temperature corrosion and erosion resistant alloys and coatings (e.g., to use seamless ferritic and austenitic alloy steels for superheater, reheater and other specific zones. Materials may be Grade T11, T22, T91 or, the like). To augment further operating conditions of the steam plants, intense research to develop cost-effective conducive quality materials is required. Proper water quality maintenance and regular monitoring and remedial actions/replacements of tubes etc. are necessary that show signs of material degradation.

c) **Boiler tube failures :**

Challenging issues: Extreme thermal stresses and cyclic loading are experienced by SC and USC boilers, which can cause failure of boiler and superheater etc. tubes due to fatigue, creep, and/or by overheating.

Possible solution: To properly design and use tubes that can withstand fatigue, creep, and overheating. Here cost of material is a factor which needs to be addressed. Advanced real-time based monitoring system to track conditions of the tubes required for earlier detection of failures and corrections.

d) **Thermal cycling during Start-up, Shut-down and load change:**

Challenging issues: SC and USC boilers experience large thermal cycling during start-up, shutdown, and load changes. This may lead to fatigue, cracking, and other mechanical failures over the time of plant operation.

Possible solution: To develop proper start-up procedures that minimizes temperature gradients and reduces mechanical stresses. To use conducive quality materials to prevent early failures and to develop advanced real-time based control and monitoring system to prevent sudden changes in material temperature and reduce development of thermal & mechanical stresses.

e) Precise control and automation complexity :

Challenging issues: The operation of SC and USC boilers call for precise control over various parameters like temperature, pressure, flow rates, stress development etc. and small deviation or error in control systems may lead to instability in operation and loss in efficiency.

Possible solution: Required to employ very advanced state-of-the-art control systems with real-time monitoring & control. Further development of predictive algorithms by integrating artificial intelligence, machine language, IOT, and automated corrective actions are required. Also comprehensive and regular, all round theoretical, simulation-based and practical, training of the relevant manpower to properly understand and operate the control systems and other necessary instruments and devices are very much required.

f) Formation of scale and fouling :

Challenging issues: SC and USC boilers are more prone to scaling and fouling. This is because of high operating pressure and temperature, particularly when impurities in the feed water accumulate. Further due to high coal burning temperature, ash may soften and develop sticky layer at the boiler tubes, superheaters & other zones and lead to local heating and hamper heat transfer due to its insulation properties.

Possible solution: To ensure stringent water treatment processes to make feed water quality compatible with operation of SC and USC boilers. Advanced coatings in tube materials may be used to reduce the deposition of scaling and fouling. To ensure regular real-time based inspection and arrangement of cleaning mechanism to dislodge the deposited materials and control scale formation.

g) Cost and economic viability :

Challenging issues: The initial capital cost of SC and USC steam generators is higher than that of conventional subcritical boilers. This is due to more complex technology, design, advanced alloy materials including costly spiral water walls, safety systems, control mechanism, and other associated costs.

Possible solution: To ensure more advanced design, operation and control systems to get improved efficiency, reduced per unit generation fuel consumption, improved reliability and reduced down downtime and maintenance costs.

h) Emission control :

Challenging issues: Though efficiency of SC and USC thermal steam power plants are high and generation of pollutants like PM, SO_x, NO_x and CO₂ per unit power production is less, still due to very high capacity of the plants SC and USC plants emit considerable amount of pollutants contributing to environmental concerns. Further Indian coal contains huge amount of ash and inherent moisture which is difficult to burn efficiently whereas imported good quality foreign coal contains considerable sulphur in most of the cases. Normally SC and USC plants in India mix about 20 to 40% of imported coal with indigenous coal leading to formation of more SO_x.

Possible solution: To incorporate advanced emission control technologies such as selective catalytic reduction (SCR) or flue gas desulfurization (FGD) systems to cut down harmful emissions. To minimize carbon emission, carbon capture and storage (CCS) technologies may be thought of. Use

of biomass in lieu of coal and if possible, incorporation of fuel mix to run the SC and USC plants can further reduce environmental footprints.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In the present investigation the basic difference between sub-critical (SBC) and super-critical (SC) & Ultra super-critical (USC) thermal steam power plants are stated. Importance of SC and USC plants over SC plants along with a detail comparison are narrated. It is shown that efficiency of SC & USC plants is quite more than that of SBC plants. Moreover, pollutant emissions, for unit power generation, are lower for SC & USC plants compared to SBC plants. However, initial investment cost in SBC plants is quite low than that of SC and USC plants. Though standardized and matured technology is available for SBC power plants, technology for SC & USC are under active developing state and under intense research arena. The various existing challenges before SC & USC thermal steam plants are elaborately explained in this present work and possible mitigation path or, solutions to overcome the challenges are thoroughly proposed.

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